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VIVONET: VISUALLY-REPRESENTED, INTENT-BASED, VOICE-ASSISTED NETWORKING

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ABSTRACT

Networks have become considerably large, complex and dynamic. The configuration, operation, monitoring, and troubleshooting of networks is a cumbersome and time-consuming task for the network administrators as they must deal with the physical layer, underlying protocols, addressing systems, control rules, and many other low-level details. This research paper proposes an Intent-based networking system (IBNS) coupled with voice-assistance that can abstract the underlying network infrastructure and allow administrators to alter its behavior by expressing intents via voice commands. The system also displays the real-time network topology along with the highlighted intents on an interactive web application that can be used for network diagnostics. Compared to traditional networks, the concepts of software-defined networking (SDN) make it easier to integrate a voice assistant that allows configuring the network based on intents.

KEYWORDS

Network Management, SDN, Voice-Assistance, Intent-Based Networking & Real time Visualization.

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DESIGN OF SECURE AND RELIABLE MU-MIMO TRANSCEIVER SYSTEM FOR VEHICULAR NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

MU-MIMO (Multi-User MIMO) has been a promising technique for vehicular networks to achieve faster communication. Conventional MU-MIMO transceiver is designed with One-dimensional (1-D) improper modulation schemes such as Binary Phase Shift Keying (BPSK) and Multilevel Amplitude Shift Keying (M-ASK) failed to yield standard ABER (average bit error rate). To achieve high reliability, a novel MU-MIMO uplink transceiver system is designed under PAPC (Per-Antenna Power Constraint) by assuming perfect and imperfect channel state information (CSI). MIMO communication channels are perceptible. Hence, security of the proposed system is improved by novel pseudorandom key generation technique using randomized synthetic colour image. Analytical design for proposed systems is carried and simulated for various p-norm constraints. Simulation results show higher reliability and security than the existing system. It also satisfies the linearity constraint of a power amplifier, which makes the system more suitable for practical applications.

KEYWORDS

MU-MIMO, Uplink, PAPC, 1-D improper modulation, Perfect & imperfect CSI, Colour Image, Pseudorandom key generation.

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ENERGY CONSUMPTION REDUCTION IN WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORK BASED ON CLUSTERING

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ABSTRACT

One of the important issues in the routing protocol design in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) is minimizing energy consumption and maximizing network lift time. Nowadays networks and information systems are one of the main parts of modern life that without them, people cannot live. On the hand, the impairment of these networks leads to great and incalculable costs. In this paper, a new method based on clustering has presented that problem of energy consumption is solved. The proposed algorithm is that energy-based clustering can create clusters of the same energy level and distribute energy efficiency across the WNS nodes. This proposed clustering protocol classify network nodes based on energy and neighbourhood criteria and attempts to better balance energy in clusters and ultimately increase network lifetime and maintain network coverage. Results are shown that the proposed algorithm is on average 40% better than LEACH algorithm and 14% better than IBLEACH algorithm.

KEYWORDS

Wireless Sensor Network, Clustering, LEACH Algorithm, IBLEACH Algorithm

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ALLOCATION OF VIRTUAL FIREWALL FUNCTIONS IN NFV-BASED NETWORKS WITH MINIMUM NETWORK COST

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ABSTRACT

NFV-based network implements a variety of network functions with software on general-purpose servers and this allows the network operator to select any capacity and location of network functions without any physical constraints. It is essential for economical NFV-based network design to determine the place where each network function should be located in the network and what its capacity should be. The authors proposed an algorithm of virtual routing function allocation in the NFV-based network for minimizing the network cost and provided effective allocation guidelines for virtual routing functions.

This paper proposes the deployment algorithm of virtual firewall function in addition to virtual routing function for minimizing the network cost. Our evaluation results have revealed the following: (1) Installing a packet filtering function, which is a part of the firewall function, in the sending-side area additionally can reduce wasteful transit bandwidth and routing processing and thereby reduce the network cost. (2) The greater the number of packets filtered by packet filtering function in the sending-side area, the more the reduction of network cost is increased. (3) The greater the bandwidth cost relative to the routing function cost, the greater the effect of statistical multiplexing on reducing the network cost. (4) The proposed algorithm would be approaching about 95% of the deployment with the optimal solution.

KEYWORDS

NFV, resource allocation, the virtual routing function, minimum total network cost

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RB-IEMRP: RELAY BASED IMPROVED THROUGHPUT ENERGY-EFFICIENT MULTI-HOP ROUTING PROTOCOL FOR INTRA BODY SENSOR NETWORK (INTRA-WBSN)

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we have proposed a Relay based Improved Throughput and Energy-efficient Multi-hop Routing Protocol (Rb-IEMRP) for the Intra Wireless Body Sensor Network (Intra-WBSN). Moreover, mathematical analysis has been presented, to calculate the minimum number of relay nodes require to be deployed corresponding to the bio-sensor nodes in Intra-WBSN. Normal sensing data from bio-sensor nodes forwarded to BNC through relay nodes while emergency data is directly transmitted to BNC. Relays nodes are placed in the patients' cloth. It can be easily replaced or recharged that facilitates effective health monitoring. The proposed routing protocol has achieved better network stability, network lifetime, energy efficiency and throughput as compared to Stable Increased Throughput Multi-Hop Protocol for Link Efficiency in Wireless Body Area Networks (SIMPLE) and Reliable Energy Efficient Critical Data Routing in Wireless Body Area Networks (REEC) routing protocols. It has been validated through simulation results.

KEYWORDS

Intra wireless body sensor network (Intra-WBSN), Body node coordinator (BNC), Relay, Wireless body sensor network (WBSN), Energy efficiency.

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AN ENHANCEMENT OF CLUSTER-BASED FALSE DATA FILTERING SCHEME THROUGH DYNAMIC SECURITY SELECTION IN WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

Today, wireless sensor networks (WSNs) are applied to various industries such as building automation, medical, security, intelligent agriculture, and disaster monitoring. A WSN consists of hundreds to thousands of tiny sensor nodes that perform monitoring tasks. A small sensor node has a limited amount of internal memory and energy resources. Sensor nodes are used to detect a variety of data in specific environmental areas. As a result, WSN should be energy efficient. Sensor nodes are vulnerable to false report injection attacks because they are deployed in an open environment. A false report injection attack consumes the limited energy of a node more quickly and confuses the user. CFFS has been proposed to prevent such an attack using a method of en-route filtering false reports by dividing nodes into clusters. However, the CFFS scheme is vulnerable for repeated false report injection attacks. In this paper, we propose an approach to prolong the WSN lifetime by adjusting the dynamic security threshold value and using a fuzzy logic-based key redistribution selection of cluster head nodes. The proposed method increases the detection rate for repeated false report injection attacks by adding the additional key distribution phase in the existing method. The experimental results show that the energy efficiency of the proposed method was increased by 40.278%.

KEYWORDS

False Report Injection Attack, Cluster-based False Data Filtering, Network Lifetime Extension, Fuzzy-Logic System.

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FUZZY GENE OPTIMIZED REWEIGHT BOOSTING CLASSIFICATION FOR ENERGY EFFICIENT DATA GATHERING IN WSN

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ABSTRACT

The energy is a major resource to obtain efficient data gathering and increasing network lifetime (NL). The various techniques are introduced for data aggregation, but energy optimized sensor node (SN) selection was not carried out to further enhance NL. In order to improve the energy efficient data gathering in WSN, a Fuzzy Gene Energy Optimized Reweight Boosting Classification (FGEORBC) Technique is introduced with lesser time consumption. In FGEORBC technique, the Residual Energy (RE) of SN in the WSN is computed. After calculating SN residual energy, fuzzy logic is applied to determine higher energy nodes and lower energy nodes using threshold value. For finding the optimal higher energy SNs, then Ranked Gaussian gene optimization technique is applied. If the node satisfies the fitness criterion, then the node is selected as an optimal higher energy SN. Otherwise, the rank selection, ring crossover, and Gaussian mutation process are carried out until the condition gets satisfied. After that, the sink node collects the data packets (DP) from the optimal higher energy SNs. In the sink node, Reweight Boosting Classification is carried out to classify the sensed DP and it sends to the base station (BS) for further processing. Simulation of FGEORBC technique is carried out using different parameters such as energy consumption (EC), NL, data gathering time and classification accuracy (CA) with respect to a number of SN and a number of DP. The results observed that FGEORBC technique improves the data gathering and NL with minimum time as well as EC than the state-of-the-art methods.

KEYWORDS

WSN, data gathering, residual energy, fuzzy logic, Ranked Gaussian gene optimization, data classification, Reweight Boosting Classification

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A MARKOVIAN MODEL FOR INTERNET OF THINGS APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

Internet of Things (IoT) allows communication among human-to-things, things-to-human, and things-to-things that are incorporated into an information networks allowing automatic information interchange and the processing of data at real time. In this paper, we conduct a performance analysis of a real application defined through four traffic classes with the priorities present in smart cities using Continuous Time Markov Chains (CTMC). Based on a finite capacity queuing system, we propose a new cost-effective analytical model with a push-out management scheme in favor of the highest priority (emergency) traffic. Based on the analytical model, several performance measures for different traffic classes have been studied extensively including blocking probability; push out probability, delay, channel utilization as well as overall system performance.

KEYWORDS

Performance analysis, Markov chain, IoT

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